

RADIANT CREATOR WORKSHOP - “Meeting the Acorns”

Date and Location: 16th – 17th November 2024, Montemor-o-Novo, Portugal

Hosted by: Freixo do Meio (FDM)

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Executive Summary

The aim of the **RADIANT CREATOR WORKSHOP – “Meeting the Acorns”** was to showcase the importance of acorns in human consumption nowadays. Actual challenges related to the climate and socioeconomic crisis create uncertainty, which further highlights the importance of proactive nature-based strategies. Acorns, as a fruit from native and spontaneous trees of Europe (but also from the entire temperate zone of the northern hemisphere) offer a potential contribution to the necessary adaptation of food systems. However, Acorn still requires coordinated efforts to become widely accessible and accepted. Bringing together stakeholders and consumers provided the opportunity to promote this UC and its real potential. This CREATOR workshop, held alongside **the II Acorn Symposium** in Portugal, brought together a diverse group of researchers, specialists, farmers, and consumers, who all share a commitment to a sustainable future for agriculture and food systems. The event featured a range of activities designed to inspire and educate participants, including presentations, field demonstrations showcasing acorn harvesting and processing techniques, tastings of acorn-based foods, and an open *Acorn Sunday Market* where local products were showcased and sold.

1. Introduction

1.1 Background to Freixo do Meio and objectives

Montado do Freixo do Meio (FDM) (<https://freixodomeio.pt/>) is a small/medium enterprise (SME) which manages a property of 600 ha in Montemor-o-Novo in the south of Portugal. Since 1990, it adopted the montado/dehesa agroforestry system as its model in search for a true sustainable model for the land. One of the first certified organic farms in Portugal, it was also the first to be fully certified in its over 300 products derived from the Montado. To ensure the land is used to truly serves the people, FDM created a cooperative of users, which includes the FDM, workers, consumers and associated producers and labours at the property. Through this model, FDM produces meat from cows, sheep, pigs and chickens, all raised in the field. Additionally, vegetables and fruits are produced in various ways, integrating knowledge and innovative trials, while also encouraging the use of wild fruits and vegetables. On the property, seven small factories collaborate to process FDM products, ranging from bread to sausages and more, and to distribute them to consumers. It provides food to local consumers and families enrolled to the CSA (Consumer Support Agriculture) program, where consumers participate in the production process and decision-making to raise awareness about sustainability challenges. Besides production, there is also a long commitment to biodiversity and natural values being one of their objectives, alongside the conservation of wild species and harmonize biodiversity with agriculture, livestock and other human activities. The whole property is now in the process of becoming the second recognised private protected area in Portugal as a representative for the Montado/dehesa EU priority habitat. This management also involves significant research and experimental activities, along with a long-standing collaboration with universities, institutes, NGOs, and other entities. These efforts aim to develop alternative techniques and strategies to address key challenges such as soil conservation, water quality, sustainable use, and the effects of climate change. This led to various publications and scientific papers with significant media exposure and recognition. The farm was highlighted as an example of climate change mitigation in the European

Environment Agency Report No 4/2019. **FDM has a long experience in using and promoting Underutilised Crops (UCs) such as wild sources of food** (acorns, wild fruit jams, edible wild plants and roots, mushrooms, etc.), **ancient varieties** (regional varieties of legumes, corn, etc.) and **new crops to the region** (lupin, quinoa, etc.). It has been involved in several initiatives and projects for the development of new techniques and has also served as a platform for many experiments.

In the RADIANT project, FDM leads an AURORA Farm growing multiple UCs. The DVC model implemented here has existed since the beginning of the 20th century and prioritizes the restoration of soil and the different extracts of the system (tree, shrub and herbaceous) based on complex ecosystems and natural and local fertility cycles. It has a unique multifunctional concept, where forestry, agriculture and livestock, fruit and vegetables, food processing and distribution, food retailing, environmental services, and energy production activities are managed at the same time and occupying the same space. FDM conducts participatory breeding activities including the selection of the sweetest acorn trees, performed in collaboration with the local community that has gathered empirical knowledge on the acorn quality throughout decades of cultivation. Furthermore, FDM conducts field trials with acorn and jujube establishing two agroecological orchards of holm oaks producing sweet acorns and jujube plants. These orchards employ agroecological practices inspired by agroforestry principles, emphasizing high-density woody plants and creating a dynamic interaction of time and space within the systems established. Furthermore, FDM provides seeds for nutritional analysis and provides data for LCA and RADIANT-metrics.

The main objective of this workshop was to showcase the potential of UCs – acorns – as a sustainable and underutilised food resource while fostering collaboration among stakeholders to support their integration into modern food systems. The event featured a panel of Portuguese and Spanish experts, who delivered presentations on diverse topics including the history, agroecology, research, food industry, production technology, and economic aspects of acorns

in the Iberian Peninsula. Participants also had the opportunity to engage in hands-on activities, such as acorn food tastings and a visit to the RADIANT UCs plots, acorn harvesting and processing facilities. These visits offered insights into the cultivation of sweet acorns and jujube in RADIANT plots, as well as demonstrations of acorn harvesting, processing, and the production of acorn-based products (e.g. acorn bread). On the second day, the workshop hosted an open Sunday Acorn Market, which included a guided mushroom-picking walk and showcased acorns alongside other locally sourced produce, further emphasizing their cultural and economic value.

1.2 Workshop framework and participants

During the two-days event around 60 participants (researchers, experts, farmers and stakeholders) attended the different activities.

2. Presentations

The series of presentations and discussions featured during the event are summarized below. This workshop was organized in six sessions of presentations on 1st day (16th November).

Session 1 - Welcome and Introduction

Alfredo Sendim, FDM & Olímpio Galvão, Montemor-o-Novo Mayor

Alfredo Sendim, FDM manager, gave a short introduction to the workshop and the FDM Farm. Alfredo shared his extensive experience in the valorization of acorns from different *Quercus* species, starting with the development of products for human consumption to their importance in

the preservation and sustainability of Montado landscapes. The session also featured a presentation of the RADIANT project, highlighting the work carried out at FDM to promote this resource. The Mayor of Montemor-o-Novo, Olímpio Galvão, emphasized the significance of acorn valorization for regional development and its alignment with the municipality's agricultural policies.

Olímpio Galvão, Montemor-o-Novo Mayor

Session 2 - The acorn in the history of the Iberian Peninsula *Enrique García Gómez, Universidad Complutense de Madrid, Spain*

Enrique Gómez is a Professor of Environmental Science. During his talk, he discussed the history of acorns in the Iberian Peninsula, and provided a cultural, social, and artistic perspective. He also highlighted the significant presence of *Quercus* and acorns throughout the various historical periods of the Iberian Peninsula, from antiquity to the present day.

Session 3 - Sustainable management and certification of Quercineas forests

João Carvalho, UTAD & Confraria da Bolota, Portugal

João Carvalho is a Professor at the Universidade de Trás-os-Montes e Alto Douro (UTAD) and member of “Confraria da Bolota”. His research focuses on Sustainability in agri-food and forestry ecosystems. In this workshop, Professor João discussed the multifunctional and sustainable management of Quercus species, as well as certification in acorn production.

Session 4 - Creating value for a sustainable diet: nutritional and functional characteristics of acorns

Manuela Pintado, Professor, Universidade Católica do Portuguesa, Porto, Portugal

Manuela Pintado is a Professor at the School of Biotechnology of the Portuguese Catholic University (ESB-UCP) and the Director of CBQF. Her research focuses on the development, compositional characterization and validation of bioactivity of functional ingredients and study applications on the development of novel functional foods and other added value applications. In this

workshop, Professor Manuela highlighted the various projects related to the valorization of acorns as a food of the future, emphasizing that this valorization must be approached holistically, within the context of a sustainable diet.

Session 5 - Integrated valorization of acorns as a Portuguese raw material for differentiating food products – Oakfood Project.

Silvia Moreira, Food4Sustainability CoLAB, Portugal

Silvia Moreira is currently a by-product valorization & management specialist at Food4Sustainability Portuguese CoLab. She presented the Oakfood project (<https://www.food4sustainability.org/oakfood>), which aims to revalorize acorns as an innovative ingredient for new food products. This initiative focuses on developing a national network of acorn producers, optimizing harvesting and processing techniques for use in the food industry for human consumption, and creating innovative products based on acorns and their by-products.

Session 6 - Socio-economic study of the acorn value chain in the Mediterranean Basin - MEDACORNET project.

Pedro Babo, Landratech, Portugal

Pedro Babo is the co-founder and scientific director of LANDRATECH, LDA, and holds a PhD in Biomedical Engineering. LandraTech is a biotechnology company that leverages the latest technologies to develop new, sustainable, and healthy food products. In particular, the company focuses on creating acorn-based products and reviving this food as a source of nutrition for humans.

In this session, Dr. Pedro discussed the PRIMA-MEDACORNET project (<https://medacornet.eu/>), which aims to promote adherence to the Mediterranean diet by introducing innovative acorn-based products and digital platforms that encompass the entire production chain.

3. Visit to Acorn transformation and producing units & RADIANT plots

On the afternoon of November 16, participants visited the FDM Acorn Processing and Transformation units. The visit began with a tour of the production unit for acorn-based products (e.g., acorn bread), followed by an overview of the entire acorn processing facility. Next, participants engaged in a field visit where the acorn harvesting methods used at FDM were demonstrated.

During Session 8, participants visited the RADIANT plots at FDM, where they observed the cultivation of agroecological orchards featuring Sweet Acorn and Jujube trees. These orchards were established following agroforestry practices, which include the planting of companion plants, row/fence planting, irrigation during the first two years, application of compost, mulching with wood chips and straw, application of effective microorganisms, and inter-row cultivation with legumes for ground cover.

FDM unit for acorn bread production

Alfredo Sendim demonstrating FDM acorn process unit

Acorn harvesting technique at FDM

Acorn harvesting technique at FDM

Visit to acorn processing units

Visit to **RADIANT** plots

4. Acorn Degustation Lunch Menu

As part of the workshop, participants enjoyed a unique gastronomic experience with an acorn-based degustation menu at FDM. This activity offered an opportunity to explore the use of sustainable and locally sourced natural resources as acorns, aligning with the principles of biodiversity conservation and agroecological practices. The lunch provided a welcoming environment, fostering informal interactions among participants. The menu showcased the versatility of acorns as an ingredient (e.g. acorn burger, acorn bread), raising awareness about sustainable and innovative dietary practices.

Salty Acorns

Acorn Pâté

Acorn Bread

Acorn Burger with potatoes and salad

Acorn Brownie

Workshop participants enjoyed the acorn degustation menu

5. Acorn Sunday Market

The second day of the workshop (November 17th) focused on the ‘Sunday Market’, one of the most popular events in FDM. This farmers' market is designed to increase the link between farmers and consumers, offering a full-day programme in a family atmosphere. Visitors had the chance to sample the local products, making it an ideal event for those looking for unique gastronomic experiences. The market opened at 9 am, featuring a wide variety of regional food products, plants, handicrafts and other local products with special attention to acorn products. In addition, the programme included a guided mushroom-picking tour, where participants had the opportunity to explore the surrounding Montado natural environment while learning about the different types of mushrooms and sustainable picking practices.

Acorn Sunday Market. A-F. Freixo do Meio products; G-I. Different local producers at the market; J. Guided mushroom picking tour.

Annex I – Workshop Program

Day 1 – “II symposium Acorn for Human Consumption & RADIANT CREATOR WORKSHOP” (16th November)

“II symposium Acorn for Human Consumption”. This symposium will bring together a panel of Portuguese and Spanish experts on topics such as history, agroecology, research, food industry, production-technology and economics of Acorn in the Iberian Peninsula.

10h00 **Session 1 – Welcome and Introduction**

Montemor-o-Novo Mayor, Alfredo Sendim (*Activities in Portuguese and Spanish*)

10h15 **Session 2 – The acorn in the history of the Iberian Peninsula**

Enrique García Gómez, Universidad Complutense de Madrid (*Activities in Portuguese and Spanish*)

10h45 **Session 3 - Sustainable management and certification of Quercineas forests**

João Carvalho, Ana Fonseca and Pedro Babo, Confraria da Bolota (*Activities in Portuguese*)

11h15 **Coffee break**

11h30 **Session 4 - Creating value for a sustainable diet: nutritional and functional characteristics of acorns.**

Manuela Pintado, Universidade Católica do Porto (*Activities in Portuguese and English*)

12h30 **Lunch – Acorn Degustation Menu** (Cantina Cabana dos Bois – Freixo do Meio)

14h00 **Session 5 – Integrated valorization of acorns as a Portuguese raw material for differentiating food products – Oakfood Project.**

Silvia Moreira, Food4Sustainability CoLAB (*Activities in Portuguese and English*)

15h00 **Session 6 - Socio-economic study of the acorn value chain in the**

Mediterranean Basin - MEDACORNET project.

Pedro Babo, Landratech (*Activities in Portuguese and English*)

15h30 **Session 7** – Visit to Acorn Processing and Transformation

Units

Alfredo Sendim (*Activities in Portuguese, Spanish and English*)

16h30 **Session 8** – Visit to Radiant UCs Plots (Sweet Acorn and Jujube)

Alfredo Sendim and Ana Vasconcelos (*Activities in Portuguese, Spanish and English*)

17h30 **End** of day 1

Dinner in Lavre at typical restaurant “Maçã”

Day 2 – “Acorn Sunday Market” (17th November)

This is the most popular Freixo do Meio farmers’ market. An event that, mainly wants to raise the bond between farmers and consumers. A full day program in a **very family friendly** atmosphere.

09h00 **Market opening & Yoga**

Regional Food products, plants, handicraft, etc. Local products tasting.

10h00 **Opening to mushroom picking walk** (*Activity in Portuguese and English*)

12h30–14h **Lunch** – Delights of the Montado: Acorn Burger or Traditional Montado Stew.

14h00 **Market continues**

16h00 **Market & Workshop End**

